

Distributed Network Tomography for Failure Localization

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Abstract—In today’s complex and interconnected networks, efficiently and accurately identifying performance degradation and failures is essential for service management, application performance, and network reconnaissance. Network Tomography can infer the state of the internal elements of the network via end-to-end measurements from the periphery of the network. Existing solutions rely on a centralized approach where the measures taken by the monitors are processed and analyzed by a central unit, or they assume that monitors can share all the information gained by communicating through a different, independent and non-faulty network. In this paper, we present D²NeT (Distributed and Dynamic Network Tomography) an innovative approach to network monitoring that extends the principles of network tomography by enabling a real-time and decentralized monitoring solution. We propose a framework based on distributed interactions among monitoring nodes, incorporating an advanced Bayesian decision-making support system. We validate our solution by testing it on emulated networks showing that it outperforms other baseline and state-of-the-art solutions in static failure scenarios. We then considered D²NeT in a dynamic scenario with ongoing failures and restorations, demonstrating its exceptional ability to promptly detect sudden changes in the nodes’ state.

I. INTRODUCTION

Efficiently identifying and pinpointing performance degradation within networks is vital for various network management functions and applications, including service provisioning, migration, flow routing, and performance assessment. However, inherent failure or congestion detection mechanisms are often unavailable or insufficient due to potential “silent” issues due to software bugs or configuration errors. Additionally, complex networks face protocols or policy barriers resulting from interconnecting administrative domains or the lack of unified monitoring services. Although low-level failures can be detected by in-network mechanisms, many high-level failures can only be observed through end-to-end connections. Network state inference through end-to-end measurements goes under the name of *Network Tomography*. The challenge with end-to-end measurements is that observations are coarse-grained; for

example, if a measurement reveals a failure, we can only infer that at least one failed element exists on the monitoring path but not the precise number or locations of failures. Moreover, the ability to locate such failures is limited by the set of observable paths, which, in turn, depends on the location of clients and servers within the network [1].

Traditional network tomography approaches require collecting end-to-end measurements at a central processing location, resulting in scalability issues, poor responsiveness to rapid changes in the observed scenarios, and lack of fault tolerance. Furthermore, this kind of approach is hard to implement in practice, especially when the failure of some nodes disconnects the network’s graph. Solving this problem requires a distributed tomography framework that does not depend on a centralized manager. Existing solutions assume that network routers run a static routing protocol, unable to route around heavily congested areas and outages, thus causing the failure of a path crossing malfunctioning nodes. This assumption allows us to consider the outcome of a path probe as certain and unambiguous. However, we emphasize that routing protocols are rarely static, with the exception of very small or stub networks [2]. While classic solutions can be supported in centralized networks such as Software Defined Networks [3], the Network Tomography literature lacks realistic solutions for distributed environments with dynamic, uncontrollable routing.

We propose D²NeT (Distributed and Dynamic Network Tomography), a new monitoring algorithm which addresses these challenges and enables continuous assessment of the network state and rapid identification of performance issues through a distributed collaborative framework. With D²NeT, network monitors implement a Bayesian decision approach to request new measurements from other monitors, optimizing knowledge freshness and consistency, while collectively constructing an incrementally accurate, real-time view of the network state. By exchanging information with other monitors, a monitor can pinpoint failures in a specific area of interest, offering crucial information to applications needing up-to-date network state knowledge. This is the case for several applications in real-world scenarios, such as content delivery, edge caching and Information-Centric Networks, and service deployment. Each monitor iteratively selects the best action (i.e., path probe

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and information exchange) adaptively relying on progressively acquired information, maximizing network knowledge while minimizing the number of exchanged messages.

The main contributions of this paper are the following:

- 1) We propose D²NeT, a novel approach to network monitoring that extends the basic concepts of network tomography to a distributed monitoring scenario. With D²NeT, network monitors act as collaborative nodes aiming to exchange their measurements and infer the binary state (working or failed) of the network nodes. We prove that this approach provides a bounded approximation of the optimal solution.
- 2) We introduce a novel utility function for choosing the optimal monitor to contact in each iteration of D²NeT. This function provides an estimate of the probabilities of node failures. Our analysis reveals that calculating precise probabilities demands an exponential number of operations. To address this, we extend the concept of *failure centrality* introduced in [4] adapting it to approximate failure probabilities in a distributed setting.
- 3) We evaluate D²NeT against previous solutions adapted to a distributed monitoring framework. Our experiments show that D²NeT outperforms the other solutions in all the experimental configurations in a static failure scenario. We extended our evaluation of D²NeT to a dynamic setting, with ongoing failures and restorations of network components, showing its ability to recognize sudden changes in the nodes' state and promptly adapt to them.

II. RELATED WORKS

Network tomography is an approach to network monitoring based on end-to-end path probing to localize performance degradation and network failures. Several previous works on network tomography aim to identify additive link metrics, for instance, delay; by looking for optimal monitor placement and probing path selection, e.g., [5], [6], [7], [8]. Non-additive tomography studies non-linear relationships between the paths and their component metrics, as in the case of congestion or failure localization. The work in [9], and more recently in [10], [11], [12] addressed problems of optimal design of monitoring paths and characterization of the fundamental limits to failure identifiability [1], [13], all working under the assumption of a bounded number of failed components. A limitation of existing solutions is that although tomographic approaches rely on end-to-end measurement performed by distributed network monitors, they require gathering all measurements in a unique site for centralized processing [14], [15], [16], [17]. The work in [18] provides a probabilistic model for inferring the most likely congested links given certain path probes. In contrast to our approach, their method is centralized and does not describe a way for selecting path probes, but rather a model to interpret the outcomes of the measurements. Similar considerations hold for the work in [19]. The work in [20] aims at finding the routing matrix that minimizes the number of paths to identify k failures in a network. We differ from this approach, as we assume non-controllable routing and

unknown number of failures. To the best of our knowledge, the works in [21], [22] are the only ones in the literature to propose a distributed approach for network tomography. Unlike this paper, the work in [21] proposes a way to divide the network into different management areas, which are split to maximize distinguishability. Network managers still follow a centralized approach in their respective areas by controlling a number of monitors. In the framework proposed in [22], all nodes are monitor nodes and share observations about their end-to-end measurement paths, to solve the linear system that models the relationship between link and path delays. Nevertheless, the work does not detail the communication procedure among monitors. Other works provide distributed or peer-to-peer (P2P) network monitoring with technologies that do not employ network tomography [23], [24]. Unlike this work, our proposed framework does not need to install software on the network switches, which is impractical in multi-domain contexts. PeerMon [25] is a monitoring system for P2P networks for assessing resource usage. The work in [26] presents a framework for traffic monitoring in blockchain networks. Unlike our approach, the anomalies detected by this framework are caused by malicious users altering the flows and monitors not sharing their evaluations or cooperating in the monitoring systems.

III. PROBLEM FORMULATION

We model a network as a graph $G = (V, E)$, where V is the set of nodes and E is the set of edges connecting them. We call $S \subset V$ the set of *monitors*, i.e., nodes able to begin and complete a transaction and serving as both a server and a client in the distributed protocol. Monitors are interested in cooperating to monitor the network through end-to-end measurements. In particular, each monitor s is interested in knowing the state of the nodes of a set of interest, $SoI_s \subseteq V$, and it communicates with other monitors to share its knowledge. Depending on the application, the set of interest for a monitor might include only nodes that it directly covers, or it might also include nodes in other regions of the network, as in geographically distributed server architectures. For instance, in content delivery problems, a monitor might be interested in acquiring information about a remote network area where the application running on the monitor intends to deploy some data [27]. For each pair of monitors (s_1, s_2) , we denote $p(s_1, s_2)$ as the path used by the monitors to communicate, in the absence of failures, or when there are no heavily congested nodes. This path is typically the shortest one. A path between two monitors is modeled as the set of nodes it traverses. Driven by the Boolean Network Tomography (BNT) formalization, we assume that the state of the nodes is binary: *working* or *failed*. A node fails if it is heavily congested and unable to process incoming traffic, or if it does not function. A path is *working* if it only traverses working nodes and *failed* otherwise. If the path $p = p(s_1, s_2)$ fails, a packet transmitted between s_1 and s_2 is bound to be lost, experience anomalous delays, or be dynamically rerouted through another working path $p' = p'(s_1, s_2)$; depending on the specific

routing algorithm implemented by the network routers. In the latter case, monitors s_1 and s_2 would still be able to communicate, and the fact that p fails might go unnoticed. This scenario is usually neglected by classic tomography solutions. Nevertheless, if their *SoIs* include nodes in p , monitors are strongly interested in knowing whether the communication passed through p , or through an alternative path, p' . We assume that travelling through p' would result in a higher delay that the monitor can detect as anomalous. Dropping this assumption would require a complex probabilistic analysis of the reliability of a path probe, which we reserve as future work.

To carry out the monitoring activity, each monitor s stores the information about the outcomes of the end-to-end paths at time n in three structures: the set of working nodes $W_s^{(n)}$, the set of failed nodes $F_s^{(n)}$ and the set of failed monitoring paths $\mathcal{F}_s^{(n)}$. Initially, $W_s^{(0)} = F_s^{(0)} = \mathcal{F}_s^{(0)} = \emptyset, \forall s \in S$. As monitors begin their monitoring activity, their knowledge of the state of the network increases and, at each iteration n , the three sets are updated. We denote with $\hat{p}^{(n)}$ the set $p \setminus W_s^{(n)}$. A monitor can observe the outcome of the paths it actively probes, and request information from other monitors. We assume that no monitor knows the number of failed nodes in the network.

1) Strategy for failed paths detection under reactive routing:

If a path $p = p(s_1, s_2)$ fails and the communication between s_1 and s_2 travels through an alternative path $p' = p'(s_1, s_2)$, as a consequence of re-routing, we shall be able to state that p is not working, i.e., to notice that the traffic travelled through another working path. We want to get this information without relying on communication heavy utilities such as traceroute, to which intermediate nodes might not respond. In a setting where the delay on a path is proportional to its hop-length, if the number of hops of p' , $|p'|$, is higher than those of p , the ambiguity could be easily solved by sending ping messages, setting the time to live equal to $|p|$ (e.g., using the command `-t` in Unix OS). The sender would either see that the receiver does not respond with echo replies or get the error "time to live exceeded". If instead $|p'| = |p|$, we also assume that travelling through p' would result in a higher delay. We leave the study of more efficient detection criteria as future work.

2) Stochastic analysis of path probes:

The knowledge of a monitor depends on the path probe and the information gained by other monitoring nodes about the outcome of their own path probes. As a monitor sends a monitoring packet to another monitor and notices that the path works, it knows that all the nodes traversed by the path are working. If the path fails (either because the packet did not reach the destination or experienced an anomalous delay), it knows that there is at least one failed node in $p(s, s_m)$. Each monitor exploits the information gained through end-to-end measurements to compute the node failure probability distribution. We call q the prior failure probability of nodes, i.e., an initial guess made by the monitors regarding the node failure probability. We define $\mathcal{O}_s^{(n)}$ as the set of observations collected by the monitor s up to step n , i.e., the outcomes of the end-to-end paths probed by s and the information gained from other monitors at time step

n . As a monitor s explores the network, it iteratively updates $\mathcal{O}_s^{(n)}$ and computes conditional nodes' failure probabilities, i.e., $\mathbb{P}[v \in F | \mathcal{O}_s^{(n)}]$. Performing a stochastic analysis of the collected information is useful for two reasons. First, in a generic network topology, there is no guarantee that end-to-end paths are enough to identify all failed nodes (i.e., the state of some nodes may remain uncertain even after probing all the available monitoring paths). Evaluating the failure probability of nodes provides more detailed information on the state of non-identifiable nodes, rather than simply classifying them as *uncertain*. Second, in the proposed protocol, monitors make decisions on which path to probe based on their *expected utility*, which depends on the path failure probability $\mathbb{P}[p \in \mathcal{F} | \mathcal{O}_s^{(n)}]$ as we detail in Section IV-A. Nevertheless, as shown in [14], the number of operations required to compute these probabilities is exponential in the number of failed paths, revealing the need for an alternative approach. Inspired by the research presented in [4], [14], we developed a *failure centrality* metric that approximates failure probabilities, extending the original concept to adapt to our distributed setting. Details on the formulation of this metric are discussed in the following section.

a) Failure Centrality:

We propose a novel definition of *failure centrality*, based on the concept originally introduced in [4], to approximate nodes' failure probabilities in a distributed setting.

Definition III.1. *The failure centrality of a node v based on the observations on the path probes $\mathcal{O}^{(n)}$, $c(v | \mathcal{O}^{(n)})$, is equal to the prior failure probability q if v is not traversed by any failing path and is equal to 0 if a working path traverses it. Otherwise, it is given by $c(v | \mathcal{O}^{(n)}) = \max\{T_1; T_2\}$, where:*

$$T_1(v | \mathcal{O}^{(n)}) = \left[(1/|\mathcal{F}_v|) \cdot \sum_{p \in \mathcal{F}_v} \left[1/|\hat{p}^{(n)}| \right] \right], \quad (1a)$$

$$T_2(v | \mathcal{O}^{(n)}) = q + (1 - q) (1 - 1/(\mathcal{R}_v + 1))^{10 \cdot q} \quad (1b)$$

$$\mathcal{R}_v(v | \mathcal{O}^{(n)}) = \frac{H(|\mathcal{F}_v^!| - 2) \cdot \text{avg}_{p \in \mathcal{F}_v^!} \{|\hat{p}^{(n)}|\} + H(1 - |\mathcal{F}_v^!|)}{\left| \bigcup_{p \in \mathcal{F}_v^!} \hat{p}^{(n)} \right| \cdot \max \left\{ 1; \left| \bigcup_{\substack{p' \in \mathcal{F} \setminus \mathcal{F}_v: \\ \exists p \in \mathcal{F}_v, p' \cap p \neq \emptyset}} \hat{p}^{(n)} \right| \right\}}, \quad (1c)$$

being \mathcal{F}_v the set of failing paths traversing v , $\mathcal{F}_v^! = \mathcal{F}_v \setminus \{p \in \mathcal{F}_v : \exists p' \in \mathcal{F}_v \text{ s.t. } p' \subseteq p\}$, that is, the set of all paths traversing node v that are not super-paths (i.e., super sets) of other paths in \mathcal{F}_v ; $\text{avg}_{p \in \mathcal{F}_v^!} \{|\hat{p}^{(n)}|\}$ is the average path length of paths in $\mathcal{F}_v^!$ and $H(\cdot)$ is the Heaviside function, i.e., $H(x) = 0$ for $x < 0$, and $H(x) = 1$ otherwise.

The term \mathcal{R}_v mathematically reflects the intuition behind the formulation of the failure centrality. The denominator considers the nodes belonging to all paths in \mathcal{F}_v , which are not known to be working. This term is multiplied by the number of nodes belonging to paths that fail, but that do not traverse v , and that intersect some other paths in \mathcal{F}_v at some node different from v . Notice that the term T_2 lies in $(q, 1)$. The study in [14] demonstrates that a node fails if its failure

centrality, based on the original definition, is 1. This result can be similarly extended to our revised version of the failure centrality definition.

To illustrate the idea of failure centrality, we consider a small example topology with four paths, as shown in Figure 1. First, we compute the failure centrality of the failed node v_1 for the example of Figure 1 in a centralized way and assuming $q = 0.1$. Initially, we probe path p_1 . Since this path traverses node v_1 , it fails. Hence, it results that $\mathcal{R}_v(v_1|\mathcal{O}^{(1)}) = 1/|\hat{p}_1^{(1)}| = 1/4$, and $c(v_1|\mathcal{O}^{(1)}) = 0.28$. We then probe path p_2 , which also fails as it traverses failed nodes v_1 and v_2 . We obtain $\mathcal{R}_v(v_1|\mathcal{O}^{(2)}) = 5/|\hat{p}_1^{(2)} \cup \hat{p}_2^{(2)}| = 4.5/6$, and $c(v_1|\mathcal{O}^{(2)}) = 0.48$. We then probe path p_3 , which fails and does not traverse v_1 . Yet, p_3 crosses paths p_1 and p_2 in v_2 and v_3 . Hence, $\mathcal{R}_v(v_1|\mathcal{O}^{(3)}) = 5/(|\hat{p}_1^{(3)} \cup \hat{p}_2^{(3)}| \cdot |\hat{p}_3^{(3)}|) = 0.37$ and $c(v_1|\mathcal{O}^{(3)}) = 0.34$. As path p_3 fails while intersecting paths p_1 and p_2 but without traversing node v_1 , the centrality of v_1 given the observations $\mathcal{O}^{(3)}$ decreases. Finally, we probe path p_4 , which works. Hence, we can derive that nodes v_4, v_5 and v_6 are working, and the set of possible failed nodes narrows down to v_1, v_2 and v_3 . As a consequence, the centrality of v_1 grows again: $\mathcal{R}_v(v_1|\mathcal{O}^{(4)}) = 3/(|\hat{p}_1^{(4)} \cup \hat{p}_2^{(4)}| \cdot |\hat{p}_3^{(4)}|) = 0.42$ and $c(v_1|\mathcal{O}^{(4)}) = 0.36$. In the example of Figure 1b, v_1 is the

Fig. 1: Example for node failure centrality. Red nodes are failed, white nodes are working.

only failed node. After probing paths p_1 and p_2 , the centrality of node v_1 is the same as in the previous example. By probing working paths p_3 and p_4 , it results that $|\hat{p}_1^{(4)}| = |\hat{p}_2^{(4)}| = 1$, and hence $c(v_1|\mathcal{O}^{(4)}) = T_1(v_1|\mathcal{O}^{(4)}) = \lceil 1/2 \cdot 2 \rceil = 1$, which means that v_1 is indeed a broken node.

Considering the distributed scenario, we note that no monitor would be able to localize the failed nodes. For instance, in Figure 1a, the centralities of all nodes from monitor s_1 's view are in $(0,1)$, i.e., all nodes are uncertain. In Figure 1b, the same monitor could only classify nodes v_2 and v_3 as working. This highlights the fact that the classification ability of a centralized tomography-based monitoring system upper-bounds the performance of a distributed approach, which is harder in general.

Proposition III.1. *The computational cost of the node failure centrality is $O(l_{max} \cdot |\mathcal{F}|^2)$*

Proof. The most expensive operation required for computing the failure centrality is the evaluation of $\bigcup_{p' \in \mathcal{F} \setminus \mathcal{F}_v: \exists p \in \mathcal{F}_v: p' \cap p \neq \emptyset} \hat{p}^{(n)}$. This operation evaluates every pair (p, p') with $p \in \mathcal{F}_v$ and $p' \in \mathcal{F} \setminus \mathcal{F}_v$. The number

of these pairs is maximal when $|\mathcal{F}_v| = |\mathcal{F} \setminus \mathcal{F}_v| = |\mathcal{F}|/2$. For each of these pairs, we need to evaluate $\hat{p}^{(n)}$, which is upper-bounded by the maximum path length, l_{max} . \square

IV. D²NET: DISTRIBUTED MESSAGE PROTOCOL

Algorithm 1: D²NeT: monitor-to-monitor message exchange for monitor s_m

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1  $S_m \leftarrow$  local view of other monitors:  $S_m(i) = \{\tilde{S}_i,$ 
    $\text{hops}(i) \leftarrow |S| - 1, t \leftarrow 0\}$ 
2  $W_m \leftarrow \emptyset, \mathcal{F}_m \leftarrow \emptyset, F_m \leftarrow \emptyset, K \in \mathbb{N} \cup \{\infty\};$ 


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3 bind(exchange_message, EXCHANGE_ANSWER);


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4 MAIN Routine:
5  $n \leftarrow 0;$ 
6 while  $n < K$  do
7    $SoI_m^{(n)} \leftarrow$  build_SoI( $s_m$ );
8    $s_l \leftarrow \arg \max_{s_l \in S_m} \mathcal{U}(p(s_m, s_l)|\mathcal{O}_s^{(n)});$ 
9   exchange( $s_l, SoI_m$ );
10   $S_m(s_l).t \leftarrow n + 1;$ 
11   $n \leftarrow n + 1$ 


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12 exchange( $s_l, SoI, L = \{\}$ ):
13  $L \leftarrow L \cup \{s_l\};$ 
14 Send  $S_m$  and  $SoI$  to  $s_l$ ;
15 Wait  $\Delta_{max}^{p(s_m, s_l)}$  for answer;
16 if answer received then
17    $\tau \leftarrow$  elapsed_time;
18   Receive  $\tilde{S}_l, W_l, F_l, \mathcal{F}_l$  from monitor  $s_l$ ;
19    $S_m(s_l).S \leftarrow \tilde{S}_l; S_m(s_l).hops \leftarrow 1;$ 
20    $W_m \leftarrow W_m \cup W_l; F_m \leftarrow F_m \cup F_l; \mathcal{F}_m \leftarrow \mathcal{F}_m \cup \mathcal{F}_l;$ 
21   if  $\tau \leq \Delta_{avg}^{p(s_m, s_l)} + \Delta_{dev}^{p(s_m, s_l)}$  then  $W_m \leftarrow W_m \cup \hat{p}(s_m, s_l);$ 
22   else  $\mathcal{F}_m \leftarrow \mathcal{F}_m \cup p(s_m, s_l);$ 
23 else
24    $\mathcal{F}_m \leftarrow \mathcal{F}_m \cup \{p(s_m, s_l)\};$ 
25    $L \leftarrow$  handle_failure( $s_l, SoI, L$ );
26    $S_m(s_l).hops \leftarrow |L|;$ 
27 Perform inconsistency check and update time step of new acquired
   information;
28 return  $L$ ;


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29 handle_failure( $s_f, SoI, L$ ):
30  $\hat{S} \leftarrow S_m \setminus S(i) \quad \forall s_i \in L \quad \forall s_i \text{ s.t. } p(s_m, s_i) \in \mathcal{F}_m;$ 
31  $\hat{S} \leftarrow$  sort  $\hat{S}$  increasingly by the number of hops from  $s_f$ ;
32 do
33   Pick  $s_l$  as the first element of  $\hat{S}$ ;
34    $L \leftarrow$  Request  $s_l$  to run exchange( $s_f, SoI, L$ );
35   if Request fails then
36      $\mathcal{F}_m \leftarrow \mathcal{F}_m \cup p(s_m, s_l);$ 
37      $\hat{S} \leftarrow \hat{S} \setminus \{s_l\};$ 
38   else
39     exchange( $s_l, SoI$ );
40     return  $L$ ;
41 while  $\hat{S} \neq \emptyset;$ 
42 return  $S$ ;


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43 EXCHANGE_ANSWER( $s_l$ ) Callback:
44 Receive  $SoI_r$  from monitor  $s_l$ ;
45 Send  $\tilde{S}_m$ , and crossing_paths( $s_m, SoI_r$ ) to monitor  $s_l$ ;
46  $S_m(s_l).hops \leftarrow 1;$ 

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Algorithm 1 details the proposed distributed message exchange protocol D²NeT. Each monitor s_m maintains a list S_m which includes the view of each monitor i known by s_m (\tilde{S}_i), their hop distance $\text{hops}(i)$ (in number of monitors, that is 1 if a direct working path exists, and > 1 otherwise),

and t , representing the last time step when s_m communicated with i). The field $hops(i)$ is initialized as $|S| - 1$, as initially monitors do not know if direct paths to other monitors exist. Each monitor s_m also keeps track of the sets of working nodes W_m , failed nodes F_m and failed monitoring paths \mathcal{F}_m . The **MAIN** routine handles the base behaviour of the distributed protocol and constantly schedules **exchange** tasks to carry out monitoring activities. Each monitor runs the **MAIN** routine. Given s_m running the protocol, the monitor first creates its *Set of Interest*, $SoI_m^{(0)}$ (line 7), i.e., the set of nodes s_m wants to monitor. At each iteration $n > 0$, the function updates the set of interest by removing nodes with failure centrality equal to 0 or 1. Monitor s_m selects the best monitoring node to query as the one maximizing the *expected utility* $U(p(s_m, s_l) | \mathcal{O}^{(n)})$ (line 8), representing the utility of probing the path $p(s_m, s_l)$ and exchanging information with monitor s_l (see Section IV-A). Once the optimal monitor to probe is chosen, let it be s_l , monitor s_m performs an **exchange** with it (line 9) and runs such function on a dedicated thread. It then updates the step counter t to $n + 1$, to avoid contacting the same monitor in two consecutive iterations, as we will see in Equation 6. SoI_m is sent to monitor s_l , and the **exchange** thread of the procedure is sent to sleep for a period of time $\Delta_{max}^{p(s_m, s_l)}$ (lines 14-15) which represents the maximum delay for the longest simple path between s_m and s_l . After receiving an answer, s_m updates its structures based on the newly acquired information (lines 18-20). If the answer was received within expected delays on path $p(s_m, s_l)$, then the monitor also sets the nodes of $p(s_m, s_l)$ as working (line 21), otherwise it considers the path as failed (line 22). Monitor s_m replies to an exchange requested by s_l with the **EXCHANGE_ANSWER** callback and sends back \tilde{S}_m , a reduced version of its structure S_m , to limit the injected traffic. To create \tilde{S}_m , monitor s_m checks the time step of the last exchange with monitor s_l and sends back only those entries that were updated after the last exchange. It also sends to s_l the subsets of W_m , F_m and \mathcal{F}_m that intersect SoI_r . We collect these sets in the structure *crossing_paths* (line 45). We highlight that, in general, r might differ from m , as a monitor can start an exchange due to a request of monitor s_r after a failure, as we explain hereunder. The field $hops$ of the monitor s_l is set to 1 (line 46), as the monitor successfully answered the request. When a failure happens, and no answer is received after Δ_{max} time, a **handle_failure** sub-routine is run, handling the inability of monitor s_m to communicate with the selected monitor. If s_m fails to communicate directly with monitor s_f , it updates the set of failed paths (line 24) and tries to reach s_f by means of tunnelling and relay through other monitors. In fact, monitor s_f may be reachable from s_m through other monitors, but the state of the nodes in path $p(s_m, s_f)$ prevents the two monitors from talking directly. This could also happen in the case of dynamic routing, where an alternate (direct) path p' between s_m and s_f exists but violates QoS constraints such as hop limit, preventing the routers from converging to p' . We recall that the maximum hop count is 15 in RIPv1 and RIPv2;

Fig. 2: Two connected components in a small network. Red nodes are failed while white nodes are working.

EIGRP's default hop count is 100 and can be configured to a maximum of 255. Figure 2 shows a toy example of this situation. Failure of node v causes the splitting of the network into two connected components, $CC1$ and $CC2$. The first component includes monitors s_1, s_2, s_3 , whereas $CC2$ only comprises monitor s_4 . Assume the extreme scenario where paths cannot be longer than five hops. Monitor s_1 would communicate with s_3 through path p_2 , which is nonetheless unavailable because of the failure of node v . An alternate path exists, and it is given by the concatenation of paths p_1 and p_3 . Nevertheless, such a path has six hops; therefore, the network's default protocol would prevent routers from converging to it. With our failure callback procedure, we can circumvent this situation and allow s_1 to reach s_3 by seeking support from s_2 . Notice that, if s_2 were not a monitor node able to perform the failure callback, there would be three connected components (namely, $CC1 = \{v_1\}$, $CC2 = \{v_4\}$, $CC3 = \{v_3\}$), as s_1 and s_3 would not be able to communicate through the alternate path. In the Figure, monitor s_4 is isolated from the other monitors and cannot possibly communicate with other monitors unless the state of v changes. The function **handle_failure** (line 25) is used to try to reach the monitor s_f and, if successful, will return all the nodes that have contributed to relay the message to s_f . The number of monitors involved in the tunnel is stored in $S_m(s_f).hops$ (line 26). A failure to deliver the message through the **handle_failure** function means that the two monitors live in two different connected components and cannot talk to each other unless some failures in the network are fixed. In the **handle_failure** function, the monitor s_m reads its S_m structure and looks for the monitor which is closer, in terms of hops, to the unreachable monitor s_f (lines 30-31). This structure is initially composed of values that may differ from the actual state of the connections but rapidly corrects itself, from smaller hops to bigger hops, as the protocol runs and failures are handled. The exchanges executed in a *failure_callback* are different from a normal exchange, as the SoI which is given and passed to the "hopped" monitors is the one created originally from the first monitor s_m invoking the failure. A failure event causes a cascading set of events where other monitors connected to s_m try to reach s_f by propagating the failure (lines 33-37) until some monitor manages to reach s_f , in case s_m and s_f belong to the same connected component (lines 39-40), or until no other connected monitor can (otherwise). Once the failures have been handled, the monitor updates its value for $hops$ entry with the number of monitors needed to reach s_f (s_l in the *exchange* function). Notice that this value equals $|S|$ only for

unreachable monitors, i.e., for monitors in different connected components. Monitors that have a *hops* value equal to $|S|$ may be actively ignored for the rest of the protocol if failure fixes are not contemplated, and should not be considered anymore by the **MAIN** routine and the failure subroutine. In the same scenario, *exchange* with monitors with a *hops* value greater than 1 can directly invoke a *failure* without having to wait for an answer, as they will not be able to answer a direct *exchange* request. The list of monitors contributing to the exchange is always returned, as it may be needed to resolve nested calls invoked by a failure. When s_m acquires new information, it marks it with the current time step. If it notices an **inconsistency** with its previously collected data (**line 27**), it removes the oldest information in favour of the most recent one. For instance, monitor s might have observed the failure of a path p at step n_1 . At the current iteration n , monitor s probes the path p again and notices that it works. Consequently, it updates its data structures by removing p from \mathcal{F}_s and by inserting each $v \in \hat{p}$ in W_s and marking it with n .

A. Monitor contribution to the utility of an exchange

When a monitor s sends a packet to another monitoring node s_m , it gets two pieces of information: information on the probed path (working/failed) and information on s_m 's knowledge of the network. With the goal of *minimizing* the injected traffic to limit the impact of our monitoring system in the network while having a *maximized* overview of the set of interest, monitors should intelligently select the monitor to query at each iteration n . To this end, each monitor should pick the most *useful* monitor at each step. For each monitor s , querying another monitor is useful as it contributes to the knowledge of the set of interest of s . We measure this information by defining the *utility of an exchange*, which comprises of the *utility of the path probe* and the *utility of the request*.

1) *Utility of a path probe*: The utility of probing a path p is measured as the number of nodes whose state can be inferred by probing such a path. We denote with $\lambda_p(p(s, s_l)|\mathcal{O}_s^{(n)})$ the utility for monitor s of probing path $p(s, s_m)$ given past observations $\mathcal{O}_s^{(n)}$ and rely on the definition of *utility of an action* introduced in [4], [14]:

$$\lambda_p(p(s, s_m)|\mathcal{O}_s^{(n)}) = \begin{cases} |\hat{p}^{(n)}(s, s_m)| + |\mathcal{F}_{1,s}^{p^{(n)}(s, s_m)}| & \text{if } p(s, s_m) \text{ works} \\ \lfloor 1/|\hat{p}^{(n)}(s, s_m)| \rfloor & \text{otherwise} \end{cases} \quad (2)$$

If path $p = p(s, s_m)$ works, we are able to infer the state of the nodes in $\hat{p}^{(n)}$ as working. Furthermore, we can also infer the state of some other nodes. In particular, $\mathcal{F}_{1,s}^{p^{(n)}(s, s_m)}$ is the set of currently non-identified nodes belonging to other paths crossing p , which would be identified by probing p , see [4], [14] for details. If p fails, we can only infer the state of at most one failed node if $|\hat{p}^{(n)}(s, s_m)| = 1$. Nevertheless, as we assume that the state of nodes is unknown, the utility of a path probe is not known a priori. For this reason, each monitoring node has to evaluate the *expected utility of a path probe* $\mathbb{E}[\lambda_p(p|\mathcal{O}_s^{(n)})]$. Because the evaluation of the expected utility

of a path probe implies the computation of the probability $\mathbb{P}[\mathcal{O}_s^{(n)}]$, which requires the computation of exponentially many factors, we rely on the failure centrality introduced in Section III-2a, and therefore evaluate the *approximated expected utility of a path probe*, which is:

$$\mathcal{U}_p(p(s, s_m)|\mathcal{O}_s^{(n)}) = (1 - c(p(s, s_m)|\mathcal{O}_s^{(n)}))(|\hat{p}^{(n)}(s, s_m)| + |\mathcal{F}_{1,s}^{p^{(n)}}|) + c(p(s, s_m)|\mathcal{O}_s^{(n)})\lfloor 1/|\hat{p}^{(n)}(s, s_m)| \rfloor, \quad (3)$$

where $c(p(s, s_m)|\mathcal{O}_s^{(n)})$ is the *failure centrality of a path* and is defined as:

$$c(p(s, s_m)|\mathcal{O}_s^{(n)}) = 1 - \prod_{l \in \hat{p}^{(n)}(s, s_m)} (1 - c(v|\mathcal{O}_s^{(n)})), \quad (4)$$

and $c(v|\mathcal{O}_s^{(n)})$ is the failure centrality of v (Definition III.1). The failure centrality of a path approximates its failure probability $\mathbb{E}[p \in \mathcal{F}|\mathcal{O}_s^{(n)}]$. Note that if all nodes $v \in p$ are known to be working, the failure centrality of p is 0, whereas if a failed node exists, the failure centrality of the path is 1.

2) *Utility of a request*: When a monitor s sends a request to another monitor s_m along a path $p(s, s_m)$, it provides s_m with information about its set of interest, SoI_s . Monitor s chooses the monitor to communicate with at a certain step n depending on how useful it expects the information provided by the other monitor to be. We define the *utility of a request* of monitor s to a monitor s_m as follows:

$$\lambda_r(p(s, s_m)) = |SoI_s^{(n)} \cap \tilde{SoI}_m^{(0)}| / |SoI_s^{(0)}|. \quad (5)$$

Specifically, monitor s_m contributes to the knowledge of s as the number of nodes belonging to the current set of interest of s , $SoI_s^{(n)}$, and to the entire set of interest of monitor s_m , $SoI_m^{(0)}$, normalized by the size of the entire set of interest of s , $SoI_s^{(0)}$. Nevertheless, we highlight that monitor s does not know $SoI_m^{(0)}$ with certainty, as it does not have the view of monitor s_m 's interest. For this reason, monitor s can only *guess* $SoI_m^{(0)}$. A simple possibility is to guess $SoI_m^{(0)}$ to be the tree rooted in s_m having leaves in all the other monitors $s_l \in S$, where each branch lays in the shortest paths $p(s_m, s_l)$. We refer to this guessed set of interest as to $\tilde{SoI}_m^{(0)}$. We then scale this value for a time-dependent factor. In fact, a monitor s might want to get information from another monitoring node s_m that it had already queried in the past, as it expects that, in the meantime, s_m has gotten more information to share. We define the *time-dependent utility of a request* as follows:

$$\lambda_r^t(p(s, s_m)) = (\lambda_r(p(s, s_m)) + \epsilon)(n - n_{s, s_m}) / \Delta n, \quad (6)$$

where n is the current time step, n_{s, s_m} is the last time step in which s queried s_m , i.e., the t field of $S_s(m)$, and $\Delta n = n - n_{s, s_l}$, being s_l the least recent monitor s communicated with. The ϵ is a small constant factor that allows us to handle situations where the guess of monitor s about monitor s_m 's contribution $\lambda_r^t(p(s, s_m))$ is imprecise and equal to 0. Notice that, by setting the t entry of $S_m(s_l)$ to $n + 1$ in line 10 of Algorithm 1, it holds that $\lambda_r^t(p(s_m, s_l)) = 0$ in the next step, thus preventing s_m from choosing s_l as the monitor to contact in two consecutive iterations.

3) *Utility of an exchange*: By combining the two utilities of Equations 3 and 6, and replacing the exact probabilities with path failure centralities (Equation 1), we get the *approximate expected utility of an exchange* λ , which is defined as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{U}(p(s, s_m)|\mathcal{O}^{(n)}) &= c(p(s, s_m)|\mathcal{O}_s^{(n)})[1/|\hat{p}^{(n)}(s, s_m)|] + \\ &[1 - c(p(s, s_m)|\mathcal{O}_s^{(n)})][|p^{(n)}(s, s_m)| + |\mathcal{F}_{1,s}^{p^{(n)}}| + \lambda_r^t(p(s, s_m))]. \end{aligned} \quad (7)$$

At each iteration of the **MAIN** in Algorithm 1, every monitor selects the monitor that maximizes the approximate expected utility of an exchange (**line 8**). We note that two monitors s, s_m that can communicate through an alternative path instead of $p = p(s, s_m)$ can still exchange information about their knowledge. Nevertheless, this information cannot be possibly evaluated a priori by the monitors; hence, the contribution of $\lambda_r^t(s, s_m)$ is omitted in case of failure of p .

4) *Optimality approximation for static failure scenarios*:

Assume now a situation of *static* failure scenario, i.e., the state of the nodes is guaranteed to be fixed for a long enough period of time. We show that the strategy implemented in Algorithm 1 i.e., for each monitor to choose the next exchange to perform by greedily maximising the expected utility, approximates the optimal solution to the problem of maximizing the utility of the set of actions \mathcal{A} (i.e., performed exchanges and probes) under the constraint that \mathcal{A} is bounded by $K < \infty$:

$$\begin{aligned} \max_{\mathcal{A}} \quad & \lambda_p(\mathcal{A}|\mathcal{O}_s^{(n)}) + \lambda_r^t(\mathcal{A}|\mathcal{O}_s^{(n)}) \\ \text{s.t.} \quad & |\mathcal{A}| \leq K, \quad K \in \mathbb{N}, K < \infty. \end{aligned} \quad (8)$$

Theorem IV.1. *Let $\lambda_{avg}(q)$ be the average quantity of information gained by a policy π , and let π^G and π^* be the greedy and the optimal policies for solving Problem 8. Let K be the constraint to the maximum number of actions and h the height of the decision tree of policy π^* . Then it holds that:*

$$\lambda_{avg}(\pi^G) \geq (1 - \exp(-(\alpha K)/h)) \lambda_{avg}(\pi^*), \quad (9)$$

where $\alpha \in (0, 1]$ is a lower bound to the adaptive submodular ratio [28] and, for each $p^{(K)} = \hat{p}^{(K)}(s, s_m)$, is as follows:

$$\alpha = \frac{\min \left\{ \frac{\epsilon}{\Delta n_{max}}; (|\hat{p}^{(K)}| + |\mathcal{F}_{1,s}^{p^{(K)}}| + \frac{\epsilon}{\Delta n_{max}}) \prod_{v \in \hat{p}^{(K)}} \left(1 - \frac{q}{1 + (1-q)(q^{\partial_v} - 1)} \right) \right\}}{\left(- \left[\frac{1}{\ln(1-q)} \right] + |SoI_s^{(0)}| + \epsilon \right) (1-q)^{- \left[\frac{1}{\ln(1-q)} \right]}} \quad (10)$$

where ϵ is the same constant in Equation 6, Δn_{max} is the maximum value of Δn in the same equation. ∂_v is the number of failed paths traversing v at step K .

Proof. [Sketch.] The proof uses the results shown in [28] and [29] for bounding the solution of the greedy approach when the objective function is adaptive monotone, as in our case. Similarly to the approach in [14], we seek a scalar α that bounds the adaptive submodularity ratio γ introduced in [28]. In particular, we compute α as $\min_{s_m} \mathbb{E}[\lambda(p(s, s_m)|\mathcal{O}^{(n)})] / \max_{s_m} \mathbb{E}[\lambda(p(s, s_m)|\mathcal{O}^{(n')})] \geq 0$, $n' > n$, such that $\mathbb{P}(p(s, s_m) \in \mathcal{F}|\mathcal{O}^{(n)}) \in (0, 1)$. In this way, α is always $\leq \gamma$. \square

To evaluate our framework, we run experiments on an emulated network and compare our results with other baseline solutions for static failure scenarios. We also emulate a dynamic failure scenario and run experiments only for our strategy, as no existing solution in the literature covers this case.

A. Benchmark solutions

We compare the results of D²NeT against three other solutions. The first, Round Robin (RR), is a classical approach where, at each step, each monitor selects the least recently contacted monitor for the exchange. The other method is a distributed adaptation of the Adaptive Path Construction (APC) algorithm, previously introduced in [17]. The goal of APC is to perform end-to-end measurements to infer the binary state of the links of a network by probing the minimum number of paths. We adapt this method to a distributed environment: monitors interact with each other and exchange information based on their respective sets of interest; as detailed in [17], for each monitor, the selection of the next probe is determined based on the number of new links that can be uncovered through probing a monitor. This number must be as close as possible to half the total number of uncertain links. Finally, we also implement the Greedy for Identifiability (GI) algorithm introduced in [12], a classical approach in BNT. At each step, each monitor probes the path that maximizes the number of 1-identifiable nodes within its *SoI*. We recall that a node is 1-identifiable if, for any possible single network failure, it is always possible to say whether it is failed with certainty. To evaluate the approaches under the same metrics, we enrich all three baselines with our stochastic computation: based on the performed measurements, the baselines compute an approximate failure probability distribution over the nodes.

B. Experimental setup

We run our experiments on the Minnesota network [30], a fiber optical network in Minnesota (USA) with 681 nodes and 921 links. We deploy 30 monitors for a total of 435 possible paths connecting each couple of monitors. We consider the following metrics to evaluate the tested solutions' performance:

Number of exchange steps to converge. This represents the maximum number of exchange steps, including the ones triggered by a failure callback procedure, required by monitors to reach the maximum extent of knowledge attainable by probing the end-to-end paths. A small number of steps to converge reflects the ability of an algorithm to make intelligent decisions when choosing the monitors to contact.

Accuracy. The accuracy of a monitor s , a_s is the number of localized failed nodes in its *SoI* over the number of failed nodes in *SoI* _{s} that we would localize by probing all paths in a centralized way. The accuracy a is defined as follows:

$$a = \frac{1}{|S|} \sum_{s \in S} a_s = \frac{1}{|S|} \sum_{s \in S} \frac{|F_s|}{|F_s^{(all)}|} \quad (11)$$

Rank. The rank RK is a metric for evaluating the quality of knowledge obtained by a model. For each monitor s , we

denote with \hat{V}_s the sequence of nodes belonging to SoI_s , arranged in order of their failure centrality. If k_s is the number of failed elements in SoI_s , we search for the last position occupied by one of the k_s failed nodes in \hat{V}_s , let it be r_s . In general, $r_s \geq k_s$, and $r_s = k_s$ in the optimal case where the k_s failed nodes are in the first k_s positions in \hat{V}_s . We define the rank as follows:

$$RK = \frac{1}{|S|} \sum_{s \in S} RK_s = \frac{1}{|S|} \sum_{s \in S} \frac{k_s}{r_s}. \quad (12)$$

Each RK_s measures the number of nodes that one has to inspect before detecting all failed nodes. We also evaluate the minimum rank, defined as $\min_{s \in S} RK_s$.

Uncertainty. We define the uncertainty u as follows:

$$u = \frac{1}{|S|} \sum_{s \in S} u_s = \frac{1}{|S|} \sum_{s \in S} \frac{\max\{1; |SoI_s^{(n_{max})}|\}}{\max\{1; |SoI_s^{(all)}|\}}, \quad (13)$$

where $SoI_s^{(n_{max})} = \{v \in SoI_s : c(v|O^{(n_{max})}) \in (0, 1)\}$ is the set of interest of monitor s after the last iteration n_{max} and $SoI_s^{(all)}$ is the set of nodes in SoI_s that remain uncertain if we probe all available end-to-end paths in a centralized way. The smaller the uncertainty, the more precise the classification. If the uncertainty equals 1, all monitors reach full knowledge of their connected components. We define the maximum uncertainty as $\max_{s \in S} u_s$.

Misclassification. For each monitor $s \in S$, this metric counts the number of nodes in $SoI_s^{(n)}$ that are classified as working (i.e., that belong to $W_s^{(n)}$ and have 0 failure centrality) but that are failed, and the number of nodes that are classified as failed (i.e., that belong to $F_s^{(n)}$ and have failure centrality equal to 1) but are working. This metric is employed only in the dynamic failure scenario, as nodes' state changes can cause misclassifications, while they do not occur in the static scenario [14], [17].

When read in conjunction, these metrics provide a profound evaluation of a failure localization algorithm. While accuracy and uncertainty are computed with respect to the maximum attainable knowledge, i.e., the information that can be gained by a centralized tomography approach, the other metrics measure the performance of an algorithm with respect to the ground truth.

C. Tests

In the first set of experiments, we consider a static failure scenario. Each instance represents an instantaneous picture of the network. The second scenario simulates a more realistic situation where nodes can fail or become congested, or vice-versa, and allows us to study the promptness of D²NeT to react to changes in the network state. We consider each SoI_s to be the tree rooted in s whose leaves are the other monitors and branches follow $p(s, s')$, $\forall s, s' \in S, s' \neq s$. In other experiments, we also evaluated differently shaped $SoIs$, obtaining similar results, omitted for space limitations.

1) *Static failure scenario:* Figure 3 shows the results in the static failure scenario, varying the number of failed nodes

Fig. 3: Average scored performance in static failure scenarios varying the number of failures.

and fixing the number of monitors to 30. In Figures 3a-3e, all methods are run for the number of steps required by D²NeT to converge, i.e., to reach maximum knowledge in each connected component. The experiments prove the ability of D²NeT to acquire useful information with few path probes and exchanges. The presented metrics are evaluated with respect to the entire SoI of each monitor, even when some failures form groups of isolated monitors, i.e., separated connected components, see Figure 2. This has a strong impact on the overall possibility of achieving high performance. Despite this fact, D²NeT always attains very low uncertainty and high accuracy. The rank is evaluated against the ground truth, whose knowledge is not guaranteed to be reached when failures occur, as some failed nodes might not be identifiable. Furthermore, failures disconnecting the network graph prevent monitors from discovering isolated areas. Despite the hardness of achieving high rank, D²NeT achieves the best results with respect to the other methods. Minimum rank and maximum uncertainty show the results achieved by the monitor with the worst performance. Even for these metrics, D²NeT achieves the best results. In Figure 3f, we plot the average number of exchanges required by each method to converge. The results highlight the ability of D²NeT to acquire maximum knowledge quickly by exchanging fewer messages.

In Figure 4, we show the results achieved by varying the number of monitors in the network with 15 total failures. On the one hand, more monitors imply higher network coverage and possibly more failure identification ability. On the other hand, larger numbers of monitors increase the probability of some monitors becoming isolated. This fact is evident from our experiments, which show that the mean performance metrics achieved by D²NeT improve or remain stable when the number of monitors increases (Figures 4a- 4c), which is in contrast with the trend of the minimum rank and the maximum uncertainty (Figures 4d and 4e) since attainable knowledge is reduced for isolated monitors. Unsurprisingly, the number of path probes increases with the number of monitors. For other methods, increasing the number of monitors does not imply an improvement in their results. This is because of the increasing difference between D²NeT's and other methods' number of steps to converge.

Fig. 4: Average scored performance in static failure scenarios varying the number of monitors.

2) *Dynamic failure scenario*: We now consider a dynamic failure scenario where the state of the nodes can vary throughout the experimental period. We note that the benchmark solutions are not designed to work in such a dynamic scenario. For this reason, we only plot results for D²NeT in this section. Initially, all nodes are working. We then select some steps

Fig. 5: Dynamic step-by-step evaluation (15 failures).

in which one or more nodes can fail or be restored. We show the results over 150 time steps in Figure 5 and evaluate D²NeT in terms of accuracy and misclassification. Vertical lines correspond to the iterations where three new failures occur (red vertical line) or three nodes are restored (green vertical line), for a total of 15 failures. Solid lines represent means and shades are standard deviations. In Figure 5a, the accuracy is mathematically undefined before step 20, when the first failures occur. After the first three nodes fail, the accuracy is minimal but grows steeply until a new set of nodes fails. Overall, the trend of D²NeT is growing in the first steps of the execution, highlighting its ability to localize network failures quickly. When failed nodes are restored (i.e., from step 90 to 130), D²NeT promptly removes them from the set of failed nodes. The results on the misclassification, Figure 5b, are in line with that of the accuracy. Expectedly, as soon as some nodes change their state, D²NeT might misclassify some of them. Nevertheless, thanks to the repeatedly performed inconsistency checks, we are able to identify these situations and select the most useful probe to reduce the misclassification to zero.

VI. CONCLUSIONS

We present D²NeT, a distributed monitoring framework that implements an efficient communication protocol based on Boolean Network Tomography. Monitors are collaborative and share information with one another via end-to-end paths. No software must be installed on the network switches and routers. In contrast to previous work on network tomography, our monitoring system is purely distributed and does not rely on any centralized orchestrator for end-to-end measurement processing. Furthermore, we assume that routing is uncontrollable and dynamic. Monitors make decisions based on a stochastic analysis to intelligently select the best action at each step. We compare the results of D²NeT with other solutions, which we adapted to handle the distributed scenario considered in our tests. Our experiments show that D²NeT outperforms the other methods in this setting. We also extended our study to dynamic scenarios, demonstrating the ability of D²NeT to promptly react to sudden changes in the nodes' state. As future work, we will consider malicious monitors transmitting false information, and we will drop the assumption that the best path between two monitors is always the shortest.

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